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Chemical Constituents of *Woodfordia fruticosa* Linn.

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WOODFORDIA fruticosa Linn (Lythraceae) is a shrub and found throughout India. The plant is reputed for its medicinal values^{1,2}. A perusal of literature revealed that no work has been reported on this plant. The present investigation deals with the isolation and identification of the constituents from flowers. The identity of each compound was established by comparison (m.m.p., IR, co-TLC) with authentic samples.

The air dried flowers (1.5 kg) of the plant, collected in Allahabad, were extracted with petroleum ether (40-60°). The extract was concentrated to 100 ml. On cooling it gave a yellowish coloured solid (500 mg) (Fraction-A). Then the defatted flowers were refluxed with ethanol (120 hr). The ethanolic extract was concentrated and poured into distilled water. The water soluble portion was extracted with ether (Fraction-B) and then ethyl acetate (Fraction-C) separately in a liquid-liquid extractor.

Hecogenin: Fraction-A, on column chromatography over neutral alumina and elution with methanol, gave a solid which on crystallization (aqueous methanol), furnished colourless white needles of hecogenin³ (300 mg) C₂₇H₄₂O₄, m.p. 253°, M⁺ 430. It gave positive Liebermann-Burchardt⁴ and Salkowski⁵ tests. ν_{max} (KBr) 3450 (OH), 2940 (CH₃), 1705 (CO), 1460 (C-CH₃) and 1350-875 cm⁻¹ (spiro-ketal side chain) etc., acetate, m.p. 250° (lit. m.p. 252°); 2,4-DNP derivative, m.p. 281-82° d. (lit. m.p. 282° d).

Mesoinositol: Fraction-B, on column chromatography over deactivated alumina and elution with ethanol, gave a creamish white solid (200 mg) which on crystallization (ethanol/petroleum ether mixture) gave colourless needles of mesoinositol⁶, C₆H₁₂O₆, m.p. 225-27°. ν_{max} (KBr) 3640 (OH), 1032 cm⁻¹ (OH) etc., acetate, m.p. 215° (lit. m.p. 216°), benzoate, m.p. 256° (lit. m.p. 258°).

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Flavone glycosides: Fraction-C, dark reddish coloured compound (2 g), on column chromatography over silica gel and elution with methanol: water in a gradient from (4:6) to (1:9) gave a mixture of three flavonoid compounds. This was resolved by preparative TLC with ethyl acetate: methanol in a different proportions into Band-I, Band-II and Band-III which afforded respectively Quercetin-3-rhamnoside⁷ (120 mg) as yellow needles (from aqueous methanol), m.p. 182-84°; naringenin-7-glucoside⁸ (110 mg) as golden yellow needles (from aqueous ethanol), m.p. 225-26° and kaempferol-3-glucoside⁹ (140 mg) as small yellow needles (from aqueous ethanol), m.p. 172-73°.

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Chemical Constituents of *Anemone narcissiflora* Linn

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A large number of saponins¹ have been isolated from various species of the genus *Anemone*, but surprisingly, complete structures of these saponins have not been elucidated. The authors, therefore, undertook the chemical analysis of *Anemone narcissiflora* Linn.² with a view to make a detailed study of saponin and other constituents of the plant. The present paper deals with the isolation and characterisation of oleanolic acid, betulinic acid, β -sitosterol, β -amyryn and a new saponin olean-3-O- α -L-rhamnopyranosyl- $\Delta^{1,2}$ -ene-28-oic acid from *A. narcissiflora*.